

Smart Mission Critical Service Management: Architecture, Deployment Options, and Experimental Results

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Abstract—Current and upcoming data-intensive Mission Critical (MC) applications rely on high Quality of Service (QoS) requirements related to connectivity, latency and network reliability. Beyond 5G networks shall accommodate MC services that enable voice, data and video transfer in extreme circumstances, for instance in occurrence of network overloads or infrastructure failures. In this work, we describe the specifications of the architectural framework that enables the roll-out of MC services over 5G networks and beyond, considering recent technological advancements of cloud-native functionalities, network slicing and edge deployments. The network architecture and the deployment process is described in three practical scenarios, including a capacity increase in the service load that necessitates the scaling of the computational resources, the deployment of a dedicated network slice for accommodating the stringent requirement of a MC application and a service migration scenario at the edge to cope with critical failures and QoS degradation. Furthermore, we illustrate the implementation of a Machine Learning (ML) algorithm that is used for overload prediction, validating its ability to predict the capacity increase and notify the components responsible to trigger the appropriate actions, based on a real dataset. To this end, we mathematically define the overload detection problem, as well as generalized prediction tasks in emergency situations and examine the key parameters (proactiveness ability, lookback window, etc.) of the ML model, also comparing its predictions abilities ($\sim 93\%$ accuracy in overload detection) against multiple baseline classifiers. Finally, we demonstrate the flexibility of the ML model to achieve reliable predictions in scenarios with diverse requirements.

Index Terms—5G mobile communication, Emergency services, Load forecasting, LSTM, Machine learning, Mission critical systems, Network slicing, Resource management.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING recent years, the majority of Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) have started to commercialize their 5G networks while preparing the infrastructure for innovative

services. This new era in wireless networking introduces technological novelties such as Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software Defined Networking (SDN) [1], [2]. These solutions, developed before the migration of 4G/LTE networks, were immediately adopted by 5G for their flexibility [3]. Basic network elements were replaced by softwarized Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) installed on top of NFV infrastructure (NFVI) [4], [5]. Additionally, beyond 5G and 6G networks will leverage cloud-native network functions (CNFs) running inside containers, providing flexible, efficient, and rapid deployment of network services [6], [7].

5G networks introduced dynamic and modular capabilities in the entire network infrastructure, facilitating the integration of transport and access network capacities with automated and scalable service delivery [8]. Technologies such as neutral hosting, spectrum sharing, and network slicing have reached maturity and are expected to become well-established mechanisms in beyond 5G networks [9], [10]. These innovations foster the design and implementation of applications in various vertical domains, aligning with the diverse requirements of the three 5G paradigms: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency (URLLC), and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) [11]. Vertical domains for 5G applications include industrial automation, Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) services, smart homes, smart cities, intelligent transportation, and cybersecurity services [12]–[14]. Many enterprises also aim to deploy private 5G networks to meet specific requirements, creating standalone 5G ecosystems [15]. A private 5G network is tailored for exclusive use by specific users, merging with public 5G infrastructure as needed [16]. One PPDR service that has attracted significant interest due to its strict latency and reliability requirements is Mission Critical Services (MCS) [17].

MC services, traditionally narrowband, are trending towards broadband and ultra-low-latency services, which current solutions like TETRA and WI-MAX cannot host [18]. The 3GPP 5G standardization extensively describes MCS specifications to ensure secure, reliable, and interoperable communication patterns within first responders and business ecosystems. MCS are primarily used for walkie-talkie type applications or voice applications such as private calls and group voice calls, known as mission critical push-to-talk (MCPTT), low-rate data transmission (MCData), and mission critical video (MCVideo) [19]–[21]. The stringent requirements of MCS over 5G networks include secure and stable connectivity in emergency scenarios (e.g., infrastructure failure or connection

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link failure among core and edge components) and reliable connectivity during network overloads [22]. Adopting MCS in beyond 5G architectures will enable high Quality of Service (QoS) connectivity and collaboration through voice calls, data, and video sharing during network congestion or isolation due to infrastructure failure [23]. Infrastructure failure incidents can range from physical destruction of network components to network congestion during disasters.

This paper addresses the key questions that are usually met in smart MCS management: What design-specific architectural components are essential for effective smart MCS deployment and management, and which are the sequential interactions between critical components? What are the general deployment options for various scenarios and which are the trade-offs? How does the intelligent overload detection perform in experimental settings, especially considering diverse service requirements? We aim to propose analytical architectural specifications for smart MCS in three scenarios, the development of a general-purpose Machine Learning (ML)-based framework for overload detection, practical implementation insights, and validation through experimental results. These aspects are aimed at ensuring seamless operation, reliability, and security in 5G networks and beyond.

II. RELATED WORK AND CHALLENGES

Several research works can be found in the literature regarding architectural transformations of beyond 5G networks necessitated to host MCS applications, as well as comply with their strict requirements. For instance, [24] presents the design specifications of beyond 5G networks to support network traffic from Mission Critical Machine-Type Communications (mcMTC), a URLLC type of communications for dynamic processes (for instance industrial process control). In specific, the authors describe the existing MTC access methods, illustrating the key 5G advancements that foster mission critical application, and elaborate on the rigid mcMTC service requirements in terms of high reliability and availability, along with latency to millisecond level.

The challenging requirements of the MCS applications are further described in [25], where an extensive analysis of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the MCPPT service in Long Term Evolution (LTE) and 5G network architectures is carried out. The authors focus on representative KPIs related to temporal aspects, i.e., the call setup duration and the call latency, demonstrating that LTE architectures and associated network components barely reach the target KPI values in beneficial network conditions and cannot guarantee the required QoS in overload scenarios. On the contrary, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) deployments in LTE that drive the applications towards the network edge, as well as beyond 5G architectural frameworks utilizing network sharing models foster the implementation of broadband MC communications, guaranteeing the fulfillment of the demanding QoS requirements.

Regarding the general PPDR architecture, [26] illustrates the deployment options and the configuration properties (including availability, resilience, and security aspects) of a PPDR

vertical service in virtualized and cloud-native 5G networks in an experimentation facility. The authors discuss possible broadband PPDR scenarios and associated functional and technical requirements, while also reviewing the key enablers of 5G PPDR architecture and deployment options, including, among others, the technical novelties of massive multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antennas, device-to-device (D2D) communications and network slicing. Finally, the authors showcase the implementation of a PPDR application in an experimentation facility, presenting the on-site rapid deployment and scaling properties of a terrestrial 5G PPDR network, as well as demonstrating its availability and reliability on a field trial setup.

In this context, innovative 5G technological advancements that support MCS applications, covering public safety requirements (computationally intensive and delay-constrained tasks) can be found in [27], where the flexibility and the scalability of the softwarized architectural framework relies on small cells, end-to-end slicing, automated resource allocation and edge computing, targeting at simultaneous interoperability between the users and high service Quality of Experience (QoE). In addition, [28] describes the architectural framework of a 5G network based on NFV that supports mission critical traffic, mathematically formulating the mobility of a mission critical user (ambulance) in a dynamic radio environment (considering LTE, 5G and Wi-Fi nodes), while also conducting an experimental study for end-to-end performance evaluation. The authors concretely illustrate that the QoS of the MCS users is significantly degraded in cases of increased required throughput and a fast-moving target user; however, the appropriate design of the network configuration (multi-connectivity in mmWave access, fallback traffic splitting across LTE and/or Wi-Fi access point) can alleviate the QoS reduction.

Considering the rapid penetration of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) methods in the design and deployment of network components [29], resources, and services, state-of-the-art research works include ML-assisted algorithms related not only to the architectural considerations of MCS deployment, but also in the optimization of network-level parameters and computational resources that MCS application rely upon. Regarding the former concept, [30] outlines how the MC services can be hosted in the open-RAN (O-RAN) 5G architecture, illustrating the role of ML in the application deployment (considering an end-to-end network orchestration) and in the radio resource management (RRM). Furthermore, [31] describes the marine network architectural framework and key ML-enablers for mission-critical Internet of Underwater Things (IoUT) applications, focusing on reliable and low-latency underwater data transmission. On the other hand, ML methods can be utilized to directly optimize transmission parameters related to the strict requirements of MCS. For instance, the authors in [32] propose a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) scheme based on Long Short-term Memory (LSTM) networks combined with Q-learning, aiming at minimizing the uplink scheduling latency in a dense small-cell network that is utilized by Mission Critical Devices (MCDs), without degrading the latency of other users. Finally, it is worth mentioning that several AI/ML algorithms that have

been designed and developed for RRM tasks in 5G networks (e.g., energy efficient power control, bandwidth allocation, spectrum utilization, etc.) can be specifically adapted for MCS application deployment [33]–[36].

While the advancements in 5G networks and beyond offer significant opportunities for enhancing MCS, they also introduce several unique challenges that need to be addressed [37], [38]. One of the primary challenges is the scalability and flexibility of network slices. Beyond 5G networks are expected to support a diverse range of services with varying requirements, necessitating dynamic and real-time resource allocation. The ability to scale network slices quickly and efficiently, while maintaining the stringent latency and reliability requirements of MCS, remains a significant technical hurdle. Another critical challenge is the integration of edge computing with centralized cloud resources. Beyond 5G networks rely heavily on edge computing to reduce latency and improve service reliability. However, coordinating between distributed edge nodes and centralized cloud infrastructure introduces complexity in ensuring consistent performance and reliability across the network.

Security is another major challenge in beyond 5G networks. The distributed nature of these networks, combined with the critical nature of the services they support, makes them more vulnerable to security breaches. MCS require ultra-reliable and low-latency communications and the integration of technologies like AI and IoT introduces several security challenges. One major concern is the increased attack surface due to the vast number of interconnected devices, which can be exploited by cyber attackers and the use of AI for network management, that can lead to vulnerabilities if adversarial AI techniques are employed. In addition, data privacy and integrity are also critical issues, as the high-speed data exchanges in beyond 5G networks make them susceptible to data breaches and unauthorized access. Hence, the need for real-time data processing and decision-making in MCS increases the risk of service disruptions due to cyber-attacks [39]. Another major security concern revolves around the trustworthiness of integrated edge components or resources, particularly in ensuring end-to-end security where all network components are managed by presumably trusted entities. This presents challenging security issues, since VNFs and network components are deployed in shared physical or cloud-based infrastructure. In a fully virtualized architecture, all hardware in data centers and edge nodes are owned by known and authenticated infrastructure operators. However, in a more distributed edge network, the situation becomes much more complex, when deployments target to avoid vendor-locked solutions. The extreme edge paradigm pushes computing and storage towards the network's edge, including user devices. Therefore, security constraints in a network-integrated edge mainly involve the authentication of edge nodes, the trust model, and the distributed storage of user data [40].

To address these challenges, several strategies can be implemented [38]. Advanced encryption techniques are essential to protect data transmission and ensure privacy. Moreover, continuous monitoring and AI-driven security solutions (e.g., based on anomaly detection patterns) can help detect and

respond to threats in real-time. Regarding ML utilization, it is crucial that both network and user data security and privacy is preserved during model training and inference, for instance by using Federated Learning (FL) methods. Implementing robust identity verification and authentication measures can mitigate risks related to vulnerabilities of edge or IoT nodes. Additionally, collaboration and standardization across the industry can enhance security by ensuring consistent and effective security practices in heterogeneous or open-source network components. For MCS, it is also vital to implement redundant systems and failover mechanisms to ensure service continuity in case of an attack.

III. CONTRIBUTIONS

Despite significant advancements, existing research often focuses on isolated components or specific scenarios, lacking a holistic approach to integration and deployment of smart MCS in diverse environments. Also, most of the current studies are mainly focused on how intelligent MCS scaling can be implemented to cope with abrupt capacity increase, usually in statically-deployed network functions. Also, to the authors' knowledge, there are no studies addressing how MCS deployment can be performed in slice-based architectures, as well as under Multiple Points of Presence (PoP) design principles, where different copies of the MCS can be deployed on demand.

This paper aims to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive architectural framework for deploying smart MCS, outlining optimal deployment strategies and analytical workflows, and validating these through experimental results. The paper also proposes an intelligent functionality for MCS overload detection, and aims to quantify the model performance under different Service-Level Agreement (SLAs) requirement and KPIs. More specifically, in the present work, we present the architectural specifications of three scenarios to accommodate, support, and handle MCS services and provide clear guidelines how these solutions can be deployed over beyond 5G networks, leveraging recent innovations in network deployments (e.g., cloud native functionalities, network slicing, etc.). Moreover, upon presenting the architectural MCS deployment options, we also aim to formulate a general-purpose ML-based framework for overload detection, especially designed for one of the deployment scenarios due to data availability. A generalized mathematical formulation for the estimation of emergency events based on KPI degradation is also outlined, considering MCS-related latency constraints. We then illustrate the practical implementation on how the ML methods can be hosted in the beyond 5G network architecture and can be used to estimate general emergency events based on KPI monitoring.

In specific, the contributions of this work include:

- 1) The detailed description and overall architectural considerations of beyond 5G networks in three practical scenarios, including a MC service load increase and scaling scenario, the deployment of a dedicated MC slice for accommodating the QoS requirements of PPDR users and a MC service migration scenario at the edge. For

all three scenarios, sequence diagrams for the appropriate triggered actions are also outlined. Specific considerations are provided regarding the communication interaction among network components, traffic prioritization features for slices serving MCS, as well as MC service latency-related metrics and downtime.

- 2) The practical implementation on how the ML methods can be hosted in 5G and beyond network architectures and can be used to estimate emergency events based on KPI monitoring. We mathematically formulate ML-assisted models, we describe their offline and online functionalities (model training, data gathering, emergency detection during their inference phase in online operation, etc.) and we demonstrate how they can boost the proactiveness capabilities of the MC service deployments in real-life emergency situations (prediction of service overload, QoS deterioration, infrastructure failure detection, etc.).
- 3) The generalization capabilities of the ML models. Although we demonstrate a pre-trained Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model's capability for real-time inference targeting the detection of resource overload in a single MCS scenario, we concretely present the effective adaptation of the methodology to generalized prediction of emergency incidents.
- 4) The validation of the ML model performance in the overload detection task compared to multiple learning-based and rule-based baseline methods. We also demonstrate the exceptional performance and potency of the proposed algorithm in four scenarios with diverse requirements, providing considerations related to the ML model complexity and inference latency.
- 5) The functionality of the overload detection ML-assisted scenario has been tested at real cloud-based 5G infrastructure, using real User Equipment (UE) with an installed MCS app in the framework of Affordable5G project¹.

Concisely, the present work targets to describe an end-to-end solution framework to accommodate, support, and handle MCS services and provide clear guidelines regarding their deployment. Moreover, this paper aims to illustrate the practical implementation on how ML methods can be hosted in the architecture of 5G and beyond networks and can be employed to estimate emergency events based on monitoring of relevant metrics. The architectural solutions presented in this work will be involved in the roll-out of beyond 5G networks, enabling, among others, technologies such as ML-assisted network monitoring, network slicing and zero-touch network orchestration [41].

It is worth noting that the described scenarios target to proactively handle either sudden service outages or infrastructure damage or failure in catastrophic events that are linked with QoS deterioration. More specifically, the failure of radio elements (e.g., base stations) is not considered in this work, but we address backbone connectivity issues with the MCS server and the central core network that may occur due to infrastructure failure of key interconnection facilities or due to

increased network congestion. The failure of RAN components has been extensively addressed in the literature employing various methods, for instance through the optimization of access points placement or by using wireless multi-hop access network [42], [43].

The structure of the manuscript is as follows: section II describes state-of-the-art MCS specifications and technical innovations found in the literature, while section IV presents the architectural framework for the three deployment scenarios. Moreover, section IV also outlines the algorithmic steps that are required to deploy the described solutions in terms of monitoring routines and required actions. Then, section V presents the formulation of the ML-assisted algorithm for overload detection, along with considerations for generalized emergency events. Section VI demonstrates the experimental results and section VII summarizes the outcomes and the novelties of the present work.

IV. MCS SCENARIOS OVER 5G AND BEYOND NETWORKS

In this section, we demonstrate how beyond 5G network architectures can host the deployment of MCS applications. Without loss of generality, the deployments that are presented in the following three scenarios consider private networks, since this type of networks is capable of operating in a limited geographical area and the associated resources and equipment can be controlled and particularly optimized towards a dedicated target related to the network functionality (e.g., a private network inside a shopping mall that aims at delivering broadband services to the users). Towards this direction, the rationale of the presented scenarios is based on the coexistence of a public 5G network that offers regular services to the end-users and a private network that can provide ad-hoc services to MC users, tenants or authorities in a concrete coverage area in case of emergency. It should be noted that the public and private network deployments exhibit different QoS, priority and preemption requirements.

We also assume that the MCS application and the beyond 5G network components can be deployed as CNFs, leveraging the cloud native functionalities of flexibility, monitoring of the relevant metrics and KPIs and deployment scalability. Furthermore, both scenarios encompass the strict performance and reliability requirements of 3GPP-compliant MCS, taking into account emergency communication conditions. In specific:

- The first deployment scenario describes an abrupt increase in the MC service consumption by users located in a concrete geographical area. In the aforementioned overload emergency event, the network architecture must enable the responsiveness and the scalability of the MC service in order to guarantee that the first responders' QoS does not deteriorate regardless of the communication demand increase.
- The second scenario considers the specifications and operational steps required to provide enhanced QoS to PPDR end users in case of an emergency. The architectural framework is based on the method of network slicing, aiming at more challenging requirements in terms of vast bandwidth and low latency. Moreover, this de-

¹<https://www.affordable5g.eu/>

ployment scenario is also associated with improved data security, better system control and flexibility.

- The third scheme is an immediate extension of the previous scenario, describing how an emergency communication critical system can be deployed as a private pop-up network, maintaining the QoS in case of adverse network conditions (for instance infrastructure failure). To this end, the MC service instantiation at the edge constitutes a flexible deployment option over the network architecture that supports the communication links and related KPIs regardless of outages, poor communication quality, etc.

In the following subsections, the specifications of the scenarios' architectural network deployments are outlined, along with the interconnection between them and the information flow. To this end, the algorithmic steps that enable the automated deployment of the network components in case of an emergency alert are illustrated for the three presented scenarios. Without loss of generality, we assume that the detection or prediction of an emergency event is based on ML algorithms that can be hosted in the network architecture.

A. Scenario 1: MC Service Scaling to Cope with Capacity Increase

The purpose of the first deployment scenario is to demonstrate the responsiveness of the MC service to a sudden load increase in the utilization of the MCS application, simulating an emergency event involving an increased number of MC users that simultaneously require communication services.

1) *Architectural Considerations:* The network architecture and the respective building blocks corresponding to the MC service scaling scenario are presented in Fig. 1. It is assumed that the deployment of the Radio Access Network (RAN) and the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) layer follow the O-RAN specifications and are connected via standardized interfaces [44]–[46]. Moreover, the 5G Core network can be offered by a Mobile Network Operator (MNO) or a Mobile Virtual Network Operator (MVNO) as a service and is linked to the Central Unit (CU) of the O-RAN deployment and to the Orchestrator of the SMO layer [44], [47]. The 5G Core typically includes several Network Functions (NF), as well as various Application Functions (AFs) that are not shown in Fig. 1 for brevity.

Amongst the latter, a NetWork Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is included, as a standardized 3GPP module that collects and analyzes network data from the Core, cloud and edge networks (including data originating from the user equipment, NFs, maintenance system, transport network, etc.) [48]. In this context, the NWDAF module is designed to gather real-time performance data of the network through its standardized interfaces and monitor various network and application KPIs. Its functionalities can be further enhanced by including advanced methods for data analysis, i.e., application performance prediction and warning estimation associated with the depletion of resources in the current network or application deployment.

Furthermore, the MCS application deployment includes the Orchestrator building block, hosted in the SMO layer. It is

Fig. 1. Building blocks of the network architecture for the MC service scaling scenario.

worth mentioning that the connection interfaces of the Non real-time RAN intelligent controller that is also hosted in the SMO layer according to O-RAN specifications to the RAN (either directly or through the Near real-time RAN intelligent controller) are not illustrated for simplicity, since these network components have negligible functionality in the presented scenarios. However, it is worth mentioning that these components can host the online learning process of an intelligent algorithm, gathering data and performing the training of an ML model. In the current deployment, the Orchestrator component assumes a management role of the network services lifecycle and is also the key architectural building block that supervises the resources allocation related to the MCS deployment. Towards this direction, the Orchestrator is in charge of performing the appropriate scaling actions in terms of computational resources in case that an abrupt capacity increase in the MCS application is encountered, leading to an overload emergency event. According to the proposed architecture, the MCS application can be deployed as a CNF in a cloud-native manner, for instance as a service docker component in a dedicated MCS server, enabling the MCS end-users to utilize PPDR communications.

As readily observed in Fig. 1, the server hosting the MCS application is connected both with the NWDAF module (being capable of providing application metrics for data analytics purposes) and the Orchestrator component (that is capable of configuring the computational resources of the MC service in case of load increase). In addition, a connection link is also established between the NWDAF and the Orchestrator building blocks, allowing the data analysis outputs and predictions to be acknowledged to the latter component that is responsible for the MCS resource scaling. Finally, the MCS end-users that are located in a contained coverage area can be directly connected through the Radio Unit (RU) to the O-RAN components, the 5G core and, eventually, to the MCS server. Notably, there are several RRM techniques that can be used in the RAN part of the network to optimize the MC user/RU association, targeting to maximize the throughput or the energy efficiency of the system. Recent techniques focus on automated decisions

Fig. 2. Sequence Diagram describing the action steps of scenario 1.

for RRM, based on ML techniques and specifically on DRL [49]. Similar ML-based handover algorithms can be also integrated when user mobility is considered [50]–[52]. All these ML-based algorithms can be effortlessly integrated in the intelligence loops of O-RAN architecture [34], [45].

2) *Algorithmic steps for scenario deployment*: In the described scenario of abrupt capacity increase, it is assumed that the NWDAF telemetry module can host an intelligent algorithm for overload detection of the MC service in terms of required computational resources. The algorithmic procedure for the MC service scaling is depicted in Fig. 2. The purpose of the Network Telemetry (NT) module (i.e., the NWDAF) is to analyze the periodic service KPI metrics and proactively provide a warning to the Orchestrator in case of overload prediction. In this event, the Orchestrator will allocate resources to instantiate another MCS CNF.

As aforementioned, the MCS application is initially deployed as a CNF (e.g., using Helm-Chart) in the MCS server. Then the following steps can describe the algorithmic procedure:

- 1) KPI metrics related to the operational status of the critical emergency application are exposed from the MC service and consumed by the Telemetry module (NWDAF) at periodic time instances, depending on the time resolution that is required for the applications (e.g., every 10 seconds). The KPI metrics are related to the smooth operation of the MC service and include: (i) the current number of registered MC users in the application; (ii) the current number of active private calls (a pair of registered MC users participating in a private call); (iii) the current number of group calls (three or more registered MC users participating simultaneously at the same call).
- 2) The NWDAF includes an intelligent functionality to process the KPI metrics received by the service and provide predictions in the service behavior of the MC users at future time instances.
- 3) In case of estimating an imminent increase in the service capacity, in the sense that the current number of MCS

instances is not adequate for the incoming MCS load, the NWDAF triggers a MC service scale-up alarm that is acknowledged to the Orchestrator as an overload detection.

- 4) The Orchestrator triggers the required actions for service scalability, by CNF instantiation and allocating additional computational resources to cope with the load increase.
- 5) The MC service is eventually scaled up, by including a duplicate instantiation that exploits the additional computational pods.
- 6) The functionality of the load balancer guarantees the integrity of MCPPT, MCData or MCVideo communication traffic by the increased number of users and re-balances the load amongst the two instantiations of the MC service for the upcoming data traffic.

Finally, it is also worth mentioning that a rule-based decision can be defined to scale down the MC service once sufficient time from the relaxation of the traffic overload has elapsed. In the present scenario, we consider a continuous communication loop between the MCS server, the NWDAF and the Orchestrator module that can be sustained on a Prometheus client server base, as described in [53]. In addition, we assume that all the MNOs have a trusted connection with MCS servers, which might not be always true. In order to overcome this issue, specific service level agreements may be needed between companies providing MCS solutions and MNOs to guarantee QoS and data integrity. Alternatively, a dedicated 5G core network that is designed and maintained by government authorities for the MCS users is required.

B. Scenario 2: Dedicated MCS Slice for Emergency Events

The target of the second deployment scenario is to demonstrate the exploitation of network slicing concept that is linked with beyond 5G networks to facilitate the intervention of a dedicated PPDR team on the field in case of an emergency event (e.g., a rescue operation in a forest fire or earthquake).

1) *Architectural Considerations*: The beyond 5G network architecture shall enable the ad-hoc provision and deployment of a dedicated network slice that will be specifically used to serve the User Equipment (UE) of the PPDR team members. Through the dedicated network slice the UEs of the PPDR team will gain access to reserved network resources at the edge. Moreover, the slicing of the network components over the same infrastructure guarantees that: (i) the data are secure since the slices are logically isolated. Any sensitive data flowing through the common network infrastructure cannot be intercepted by different slices; (ii) the QoS of the dedicated slice is improved. The MCS network slice can exhibit data traffic prioritization compared to the best-effort services provided by the pre-existing network slice that is used by regular users in the network.

The general architecture of the second deployment scenario is depicted in Fig. 3, where the network components of the two separate slices are detailed. It is assumed that the best-effort slice is served by the central 5G Core deployment, whereas the dedicated MCS network slice associated with the reserved MCS resources utilizes some components of the 5G

Fig. 3. Building blocks of the network architecture for the dedicated MCS slice scenario.

Core that are located at the edge. As observed from Fig. 3, the two slices share several architectural network components, including the unique O-RAN modules in the RAN part of the network, as well as the majority of the central 5G core components. The Central Unit User Plane (CU-UP) of the RAN is connected both to the central and the edge User Plane Functions (UPFs), depending on the considered network slice, whereas the Central Unit Control Plane (CU-CP) is directly connected to the Access & Mobility Management Function (AMF) of the central 5G core. Furthermore, the regular users that are connected to the already existing (default) slice have a configuration for best-effort services, whereas the UEs of the PPDR team that are connected to the dedicated MCS network slice communicate with the MCS edge server, having a particular configuration for traffic prioritization and leveraging improved QoS.

Regarding the 5G core components, the two slices share all the usual NFs except for the UPF network component. On one hand, the UPF that is deployed in the physical server of the central 5G core is connected to the default Data Network, i.e., the Internet. In this context, the set of all the NFs that are deployed in the Central 5G core server constitutes the core sub-network of the best-effort network slice. On the contrary, the UPF for the MCS network slice is deployed at the edge 5G core and is still managed by the central control plane, through its interconnection with the Session Management Function (SMF). The second UPF, along with the core components constitute the core sub-network of the MCS slice.

Finally, the central 5G core can expose an Application Programming Interface (API) that can be used for management

configuration purposes. Specifically, in this scenario, the 5G API originating from the NT module can be utilized to enable or disable the deployment and the operation of a particular network slice. The (slicing) Orchestrator component located in the SMO layer can therefore leverage the 5G Core API and deploy an ad-hoc dedicated MCS slice in case a warning alarm is received or the intervention of the PPDR team is imminent. These emergency events notify the Orchestrator to additionally instantiate the MCS system at the edge, representing the actual Data Network for the second UPF.

2) *Algorithmic steps for scenario deployment:* In Fig. 4, the algorithmic steps required to implement the MCS slicing scenario are illustrated. We assume that a slice in the network architecture already exists (Fig. 3) and is used to serve the regular users existing in the area in a best-effort QoS manner. Moreover, we assume that an emergency event occurs (detected by analysis of system KPIs as in the previous scenario or direct notification regarding an occurred failure) and it is acknowledged to an emergency control center. The following steps are then triggered:

- 1) The emergency control center notifies the Orchestrator component that is responsible for providing the network slicing, requesting a dedicated MC slice for an emergency service.
- 2) The Orchestrator communicates this request through the 5G API to the central 5G core of the network architecture, requesting a dedicated slice for utilization from PPDR users that require reserved network resources for the emergent circumstances and higher QoS than the best-effort slice.
- 3) From the Central 5G core, a second UPF that is located in close proximity to the emergency area is instantiated as a user plane component of the dedicated MC slice, aiming at serving the traffic from the PPDR users.
- 4) Once the second edge UPF is instantiated, a confirmation acknowledgment is sent to the Orchestrator through the Central 5G Core components.
- 5) The Orchestrator deploys the required slice at the edge for the emergency service bodies or PPDR users exploiting the instantiation of the edge UPF, since the network has been reshaped to form the dedicated MC slice.
- 6) The edge MC service is eventually instantiated to provide PPDR users with reserved resources at the edge, e.g., ultra-low latency, improved QoS and secure communications.

Traffic prioritization can be also granted within the same slice for a specific user or a subset of UEs by modifying the targeted QoS through the selection of a suitable 5G QoS Identifier (5QI). By increasing the 5QI value, higher priority (including, for instance, higher bandwidth) to the traffic of a specific UE or UE profile (PPDR user) can be granted within the same slice.

Regarding data security and isolation considerations between the two different network slices, potential breaches may occur through the capacity elasticity of one slice to consume the resources of another slice [54]. Moreover, the network slicing functionality in this scenario is not end-to-end, in the sense that various control plane functions might be

Fig. 4. Sequence Diagram describing the action steps of the MC slicing deployment.

shared among the different slices (for instance, the Network Slice Selection Function - NSSF), which can be used as an vulnerability point for potential attacks. Attacks can also be initiated through the UEs, since they can simultaneously access multiple network slices and act as bridges for the attackers to gain unauthorized access. Apart from the above intra-slice (between-slice) security considerations, additional concerns are valid regarding the inter-slice (inside the same slice) data security and isolation [55]. In our work, we consider that data security methods and best-practices that are typically implemented in beyond 5G networks can be conveniently adapted and incorporated at the presented architectural framework for the MCS deployment.

Finally, it is worth noting that we have considered a static instance regarding the resource allocation between the network slices. However, many DRL-based algorithms for resource allocation problems in different network slices can be integrated in the presented architecture to enable the dynamic allocation of resources and fulfill specific QoS requirements [56]. These DRL-based resource allocation methods include radio resource slicing (the O-RAN components are shared in the described scenario), but also priority-based core network slicing [57].

C. Scenario 3: MC Service Relocation in Multiple Points of Presence (PoP)

The present scenario is considered an extension of the second deployment scenario (dedicated MCS slicing), aiming to describe an emergency situation related to infrastructure failure and highlighting the relocation capabilities of a MC service in an additional Point of Presence (PoP) that is located at close proximity to the location of the emergency event.

1) *Architectural Considerations*: In this subsection, we demonstrate the beyond 5G architectural framework that enables the seamless service migration closer to the edge, while at the same time securing the application synchronization for the MC users. In principle, the capability of an operating MC service to completely migrate from a cloud to an edge PoP is essential in an emergency event. Typically, this migration targets to overcome irregular operating infrastructure, as well as sudden critical errors that can occur in the telecommunication system (e.g., failure of a backhaul link that may cause huge details in the packet delivery). The architectural framework

Fig. 5. Building blocks of the network architecture for the multiple PoP scenario.

shall enable the service transition, switching the network traffic properly in a seamless manner for the MC users.

The architectural building blocks are shown in Fig. 5, where a single MCS network slice is considered for simplicity, along with two separate MCS servers (cloud and edge). The components comprising the dedicated MCS slice are identical to those described in the second deployment scenario (Fig. 3). Similar to the previous scenario, the Orchestrator component can be notified through the 5G Core API to relocate the MC service deployment from the cloud (origin) to the edge (destination) server in a seamless way for the PPDR users.

2) *Algorithmic steps for scenario deployment*: As already described in the network architecture of the multiple PoP scenario, the MCS service instantiation at the edge can occur when periodic service and/or system KPI metrics deviate significantly from their nominal values. These KPIs typically relate to network metrics such as QoS performance and end-to-end latency. We first assume that a dedicated MC slice has been already deployed in the network (similar to scenario 2) that the MC UEs use in order to access the cloud-native MC service (Fig. 3). In the initial status, the MC service is working in the main (cloud) instance and for instance, has been deployed as a Kubernetes Network Function (KNF). To this end, the MC users (e.g., PPDR first-responders) can access the cloud-native MC service and are normally using the service. The algorithmic steps required to demonstrate the multi-PoP feature of the MC service are summarized below:

- 1) The MC service provides KPI metrics to the telemetry system in order to monitor the performance of the MCS application.
- 2) KPI metrics related to the network infrastructure are also communicated to the NWDAF for monitoring purposes.

- 3) The NWDAF component performs a KPI analysis of the periodically received data, targeting to estimate irregularities in the latency metrics that may implicitly reveal critical infrastructure failure.
- 4) In case of emergency event detection, or due to optimal placements algorithms, manual intervention or cost-related decisions, the telemetry module alerts the Orchestrator to initiate the procedure for MC service migration. The reasons for the MC service migration mainly include QoS deterioration, service outage and infrastructure failure.
- 5) The Orchestrator investigates the availability of infrastructure at the edge, as well as allocating the appropriate computational resources.
- 6) The Orchestrator partially instantiates the MC service at the edge PoP, taking into consideration that the service needs to be relocated in a seamless way for the MC users. The service is therefore re-instantiated in replica mode, i.e., the database and the memory storage components are deployed at the edge server.
- 7) The MC service edge instantiation synchronizes the service-specific stateful information with the main instance's MC service (database synchronization including all data related to users, groups, dialog status, etc.). Please note that the synchronization is conducted 'offline', in the manner that the MCS user is still connected to the cloud premises.
- 8) The full deployment of the MC service remaining pods in edge instance is conducted and the MC users are automatically directed to start using the edge PoP instantiation of the service after seamless re-connection. Specifically, once the QoS of the MC service deteriorates considerably or the service outage occurs, the edge instance of the MCS that was in stand-by mode is fully deployed (the remaining components/pods are instantiated) and the edge node is upgraded to master node. Then, the fully qualified domain name (FQDN) of the MCS users is modified to point to the edge instance. Thus, the UEs update their FQDN resolution and are seamlessly re-connected to the deployed service in the destination (edge) PoP.

It is also worth mentioning that load and UE distribution mechanisms can be accomplished by monitoring the UE-specific KPIs and providing predictions/warnings for each individual user. Then, through the Orchestrator, the MCS system can suitably perform user dissociation by modifying their FQDN to ensure that the MC users are connected to the appropriate (cloud or edge) instance. Fig. 6 shows a sequence diagram for scenario 3, outlining the course of action of the multi-PoP feature and the interactions that are performed between the involved entities.

3) *Considerations for MC service relocation time:* On the occasion of QoS degradation detection before the incident occurrence based on a predictive model, the migration process of the MC service is initiated. According to the sequence diagram for scenario 3 shown in Fig. 6, a copy of the active MCS (running at the cloud) is deployed proactively to the edge location for auxiliary and back-up purposes. The edge instance is therefore prepared proactively without causing any

Fig. 6. Sequence Diagram describing the action steps of the multi-PoP MC service deployment.

MC service downtime. If the projection of the predictive model continues to forecast further QoS deterioration, then the actual migration from cloud to edge occurs, as described in the following steps of Fig. 6.

The above strategy can considerably prevent the system from denying the MCS to the users, since the proactive instantiation of the MCS at the edge eliminates the migration downtime. Towards this direction, the MCS instance is *a priori* deployed at the edge PoP (the service can be deployed at multiple points of presence), so as to ensure no loss of service provisioning. As aforementioned, the reasons for the service migration include QoS deterioration, service outage or infrastructure failure.

These events can be monitored in the proposed architecture through the NT component (Fig. 6). The KPI metrics that are usually monitored for the QoS degradation of the MCPTT MCS application are [19]:

- *Round-Trip-Time (RTT)*: the time required for data transmitted from the MC user to reach the application or service provider, processed and to transfer a status acknowledgement back to the UE (delay mainly due to underlying network).
- *MCPTT access time*: the time interval between a PTT press event, the token request, and the access granted (it is assumed that the call has been established).
- *End-to-end MCPTT access time*: the time interval between a MCPTT user request, call establishment and acknowledgment from receiving user before voice can be transmitted (typical MCPTT private call that the receiving client accepts and joins).

Hence, the above KPI metrics can be acknowledged to the NWDAF telemetry component periodically as time series. Then, the NWDAF can include a model that will provide predictions for the KPI degradation (for instance, the model can predict future values of the MCPTT access time, taking also into consideration the number of users that are using the MCS application).

In addition, if there is a connectivity loss between the main infrastructure and the edge infrastructure (in case of infrastructure failure or service outage), the KPI metrics will not be received to the monitoring NWDAF component. The target is

therefore to identify in advance the imminent communication failure and proactively migrate the MC service at the edge. The NWDAF component can include an additional predictive model designed for failure detection, belonging to the general category of anomaly detection tasks.

In both cases, the critical parameter is the proactiveness ability of the intelligent NWDAF module, i.e., how timely the incorporated model can predict the incoming event (QoS deterioration, service outage or infrastructure failure). Let us denote the time instance that the infrastructure failure, the service outage or the severe KPI degradation occurs as $t = T_o$, the time required to instantiate the edge in replica mode as T_{inst} , the time required to sync between the edge and cloud database and memory storage components as T_{sync} and the time required to deploy the rest of the components as T_{dep} . If the time instance of the model prediction is T_p , the duration for the migration is $\Delta = T_o - T_p - (T_{inst} + T_{sync} + T_{dep}) = C - (T_{inst} + T_{sync} + T_{dep})$ and the service downtime D can be described as:

$$D = \begin{cases} RTT/2 & \text{if } \Delta \leq 0 \\ RTT/2 + \Delta & \text{if } \Delta > 0 \end{cases}. \quad (1)$$

Noteworthy, we have inherently assumed that $T_o < T_p$, i.e., the model prediction is provided before the actual event occurrence, and that the MC users have already accessed the MCPTT services before the migration. To this end, in case of timely prediction and migration of the MCS server to the edge, the downtime D is $RTT/2$, i.e., the time required for transmission from the MC user to the service provider, which is typically in the order of ms (and the handover is almost seamless). Otherwise, the service downtime increases by the factor Δ , i.e., the duration for the migration, which can range up to several seconds, depending on the proactiveness capability of the ML model and the time required for synchronization between the replicated MCS servers. The model that is included in the NWDAF component in this case shall be therefore exhibit enhanced proactiveness ability in order to minimize the service downtime D .

V. MCS OVERLOAD DETECTION

In this section, the MCS overload detection problem is mathematically formulated, along with the algorithm used for the training of the LSTM network. Moreover, the mathematical framework of generalized prediction in emergency events is also illustrated. It should be noted that the estimation of an emergency event or a KPI degradation follows in principle the same logic and the presented algorithmic procedure can be adapted with minor modifications for all the deployment scenarios presented in the previous section (prediction for the emergency control center for scenario 2 and prediction of the KPI metrics for scenario 3).

A. Metrics Description

The metrics that monitor the service-related aspects of the MCS system are based on the number of users who have registered for the MCS service and the activity they are

engaged in. The metrics that we consider in this work are relevant to the MCPTT communication and are explained below:

1. *Number of registered users*, N_{RU} : the UEs who have registered for the MCS service, regardless of their current activity (e.g. in a call, or in stand-by).

2. *Number of active private calls*, N_{PC} : the number of private calls that are happening at the same time in the MCS service that is deployed.

3. *Number of active group calls*, N_{GC} : the number of group calls that are happening at the same time in the deployed MCS service. It is worth noting that active private calls always involve only two UEs, while group calls can involve any number of users more than 2.

B. Problem Formulation for MCS Overload Detection

MCS overload detection comprises a time-series anomaly detection problem, with the intelligent agent trying to predict the time point of overload occurrence. The agent (e.g. an ML model) employs a autoregressive model which combines past and previous values of some features (or predictors) so as to predict future value(s) of a target variable (categorical variable ‘anomaly’ or ‘no anomaly’). In this sense, a time-series classification problem is defined:

$$Y_{t+C} = f(X_{t-W}, \dots, X_t | \theta_i) \quad (2)$$

where X_t is the value of the feature vector at time point t , or analytically $X_t = [x_{1,t}, \dots, x_{n,t}]^T$ and x_i is the predictor i at time t ($i = 1, \dots, n$). In addition, Y_t is the categorical value of the target variable at time t (‘0’ denotes ‘anomaly’, ‘1’ denotes ‘no anomaly’), and $f(\cdot | \theta_i)$ is the unknown function estimated by the ML model, which maps the predictors with the target variable, for a given configuration of the model weights θ_i . Parameters C (Pro-activeness Ability) and W (Lookback Window) represent the degree to which the model predicts future values of Y and exploits past values of X , respectively. For instance, if $C = 3$ and $W = 6$, the model forecasts the value of Y_{t+3} based of the values of $X_{t-6}, X_{t-5}, \dots, X_t$ (for a given time t).

To formulate the overload detection problem, two types of dataset are required: a training and a testing dataset. The former is used to fit the model and to properly adjust the weights θ_i , whereas the latter is used to test the model on unseen data samples. During the training, various weights θ_i of the model are tested based on the degree of which the model predicts the expected outputs. The aim of the intelligent agent is to find the optimal configuration i of the model weights θ_i , so as to minimize the prediction error. The prediction error is a function that quantifies the difference between the predicted and groundtruth values of the target variable, called loss or cost function and denoted as $Cost$. A Binary CrossEntropy Log-Loss is used to represent the loss function in this 2-class prediction problem, as follows:

$$Cost|_{\theta_i} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N Y_j \cdot \log \hat{p}_j + (1 - Y_j) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{p}_j) \quad (3)$$

where N is the total count of testing samples, Y_j is the actual class label (0 or 1) of sample j , whereas \hat{p}_j is the respective probability of class label predicted by the model. As implied by (3), when the class probability is high and correct (e.g. $Y_j = 1$ and $\hat{p}_j = 0.99$), then the term becomes negligible and the $Cost$ metric is closer to the minimization.

The objective of the intelligent agent is to find the optimal value of the cost function, as:

$$Cost_{opt} = Cost|_{\theta_{opt}} \quad (4)$$

with the optimal weights being:

$$\theta_{opt} = \arg \min_{\theta_i} Cost|_{\theta_i} \quad (5)$$

where $Cost|_{\theta_i}$ is the cost function value achieved by weight configuration θ_i , and θ_{opt} is the weight configuration that produces the minimum classification error.

Each MCS instance has a predefined amount of resources that balance the service quality and the resource efficiency, based on a maximum number of users (U) that can use the MCS. Therefore, every MCS instance has a certain capacity in terms of:

- 1) the number of users that can join a group call at the same time (C_{group}) and
- 2) the total number of users that can be in either a private or a group call (C_{total}).

Let A_P be an array (of size $N_{RU} \times N_{PC}$) that has elements $A_P(i, j) = 1$, when user i participates in private call j , whereas $A_P(i, j) = 0$, when the user is simply registered but inactive. Let also A_G be an array (of size $N_{RU} \times N_{GC}$) with elements $A_G(i, j) = 1$, when user i is in group call j , whereas $A_G(i, j) = 0$ when the user is only registered. The constraints (i) and (ii) can now formally expressed as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{RU}} A_G(i, j) \leq C_{group}, j = 1, \dots, N_{GC} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{RU}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{PC}} A_P(i, j) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{RU}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{GC}} A_G(i, k) \leq C_{total} \quad (7)$$

where (6) implies that the number of users participated in a group call is upper-bounded by the group call capacity, and (7) denotes that the total number of active users cannot exceed the total capacity of the MC service.

In an emergency, to prevent the users in a single group call from exceeding the maximum capacity C_{group} , the MCS application places incoming group call requests in group calls that are not full. A situation that MCS cannot handle occurs when the number of active users (i.e. users who are in private or group calls) exceeds the total MCS capacity C_{total} . Also, the total capacity is expressed in relation to the maximum number of users, scaled by a predefined percentage ratio r , i.e.:

$$C_{total} = r \cdot U \quad (8)$$

Fig. 7. Architecture of the LSTM model to estimate the function $f_{LSTM}(\cdot)$. Softmax activation function transforms the output value to the probability of overload occurrence at $t + C$, i.e. $\mathbb{P}(t + C = OToA)$.

Thus, the Overload Time-of-Arrival (OToA) is finally determined by the formula:

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_{RU}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{PC}} A_P(i, j) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{RU}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{GC}} A_G(i, k) \right]_{t=OToA} = r \cdot U \quad (9)$$

where the left side of (9) equals to the total number of active users at time $t = OToA$, and $OToA$ is the time of overload occurrence.

C. MCS Overload Forecasting with LSTM

MCS is a service that demands very low response latency, while the scaling of resources involves a time-consuming communication between the MCS system and the network Orchestrator. Therefore, a deterministic rule-based reactive scaling mechanism is quite impractical. Instead, a proactive method to detect overload should be followed by applying a traffic prediction model that forecasts the overload situation. All the epochs in the dataset are labeled as either “overload” (label “1”) or “no overload” (label “0”), according to (9). This creates a time-series anomaly prediction problem, using the overload label as the target categorical variable and the three collected traffic metrics (current and previous values) as predictors. A Long-Short Term Memory Network (LSTM) is designed as an overload predictor and its structure is shown in Fig. 7. Based on (2), when making a prediction with the LSTM model at the present time t to estimate the likelihood of overload at a future time point $t + C$, both the present and previous values of the traffic metrics are used as inputs. The optimal lookback window W of previous traffic values considered by the model is a hyperparameter that is fine-tuned through training simulations.

The LSTM is a branch of recurrent neural network (RNN) that can handle sequential data, such as text, speech, or video [58]. LSTM differs from standard feedforward neural networks in that it has feedback connections that enable it to retain and access information for long periods of time. This makes LSTM appropriate for tasks that need long-term dependencies, such as hand-writing recognition, speech recognition and

machine translation [59], [60]. The LSTM networks have also shown excessive performance in several complex regression and classification time-series forecasting problems, where the relationship between input features and output variable(s) were not *a priori* known (as in our case). In this context, we selected the development of an LSTM model for the overload prediction problem, since it exhibits beneficial computational complexity/accuracy trade-off and because, in general, it is a powerful widely-used non-linear model, capable of identifying long-range temporal dependencies amongst multiple variables.

LSTM consists of cells that have four elements: a memory state, an input gate, a forget gate, and an output gate. The memory state keeps the information that is relevant for the current sequence. The input gate determines which parts of the new input to store in the memory state. The forget gate determines which parts of the previous memory state to discard. The output gate determines which parts of the current memory state to output. LSTM can be trained using a variation of the standard backpropagation algorithm called backpropagation through time (BPTT), which considers the temporal dependencies in the network [59]. BPTT calculates the gradients of the cost function $Cost$ with respect to the network parameters θ_i by using the chain rule along the sequence.

Algorithm 1 LSTM training for MCS overload forecasting.

- 1: Training data: Feature vector $X = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$ and labels $Y = y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N$.
 - 2: LSTM hyperparameters: Learning rate α , number of epochs E , batch size B , number of hidden layers N_H
 - 3: Learning parameters: Lookback W , Proactiveness Ability C
 - 4: **for** $e = 1$ to E **do**
 - 5: Shuffle X and Y in the same order
 - 6: **for** $b = 1$ to $\lceil N/B \rceil$ **do**
 - 7: Get batch $X_b = x_{(b-1)B+1}, \dots, x_{bB}$ and $Y_b = y_{(b-1)B+1}, \dots, y_{bB}$
 - 8: Perform feedforward of X_b based on θ_i
 - 9: Get the predictions \hat{Y}_b
 - 10: Compute loss between actual Y_b and predicted \hat{Y}_b , based on (3)
 - 11: Perform BPTT to estimate the LSTM network parameters θ_i^*
 - 12: Update network parameters via gradient descent: $\theta_i^* = \theta_i - \alpha \nabla \theta_i$ to ensure $Cost|_{\theta_i^*} < Cost|_{\theta_i}$
 - 13: Set $\theta_i = \theta_i^*$
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: **end for**
-

The training process of the LSTM model for MCS overload detection is described in Algorithm 1. The training data include N samples of feature vector X (time-series of MCS metrics) and labels Y (time-series of ‘overload’ or ‘no overload’). At time t , a particular training sample i is comprised of the LSTM inputs $x_i = N_{RU}(t-W), N_{PC}(t-W), N_{GC}(t-W), \dots, N_{RU}(t), N_{PC}(t), N_{GC}(t)$ and the respective LSTM desired output $y_i = Y_{t+C}$ (‘0’ or ‘1’). The hyperparameters of

the LSTM network that need to be fine-tuned are the learning rate α , the number of epochs E , the batch size B and the number of hidden layers N_H , with the parameters α and N_H being the most critical for LSTM convergence. Apart from these parameters, learning parameters of the algorithm also include the Lookback Window W and the Proactiveness Ability C . Therefore, during the training phase, the algorithm (i) randomly selects a batch from the training sample, (i) performs feedforward passes of the data through the LSTM model and (iii) computes the log-loss between actual Y_b and predicted \hat{Y}_b labels. Then, the BPTT algorithm is used to estimate the new network weights θ_i^* and the gradient descent is utilized to update the LSTM network parameters towards $Cost|_{\theta_i^*}$ minimization, leading to the optimal MCS overload detection capabilities.

Once the training algorithm has been implemented, the LSTM model can be operated in the inference mode to estimate the MCS overload probability at time point $t+C$, based on the input of the LSTM model covering W past values of the MCS traffic. Finally, the trained model, with θ_{opt} adjusted weights, estimates a function $f_{LSTM}(\cdot|_{\theta_{opt}})$ which maps the relation between LSTM inputs (i.e. the values of N_{RU}, N_{PC}, N_{GC} within the window $[t-W, t]$) and output $\mathbb{P}(t+C = OToA)$ (i.e. the probability of overload occurrence at $t+C$), as indicated by the following formula:

$$\mathbb{P}(t+C = OToA) = f_{LSTM}(N_{RU}(t-W), N_{PC}(t-W), N_{GC}(t-W), \dots, N_{RU}(t), N_{PC}(t), N_{GC}(t)|_{\theta_{opt}}) \quad (10)$$

Finally, the probability $\mathbb{P}(t+C = OToA)$ is transformed into a binary overload decision class O_{MCS} (‘Overload’ or ‘No Overload’) according to a predefined decision percentage threshold D_{th} , which regulates the trade-off between true and false positives:

$$O_{MCS} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbb{P}(t+C = OToA) \geq D_{th} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Evidently, when D_{th} is close to 1, then the probability of false positives is low, but it is more likely to miss true overload conditions. On the contrary, when D_{th} is close to 0, it is more likely to correctly predict all overload conditions. However, the probability of false positive is high and the algorithm will frequently raise wrong overload warnings. As a result, a value of $D_{th} = 0.5$ can achieve a reasonable prediction balance between false positive and false negative ratio, although specific applications may require different values.

D. Considerations for the Implementation of MCS Overload Detection

The implementation steps for the practical development of the overload MCS scenario can be summarized as follows:

- (a) The NWDAF is deployed as a service in the local infrastructure or in a data-center (for instance as a pod in a cluster).

- (b) A single instance of MCS service docker component in the server is also deployed.
- (c) The three-fold MCS metrics are exposed through a Prometheus exporter and consumed by the Telemetry System module.
- (d) The NWDAF typically includes a visualization tool (e.g., a Grafana dashboard) to monitor the metrics acknowledged by the MCS.
- (e) The LSTM model residing in the NWDAF is inferred (using as input the time-series of the three-fold metrics) for purposes of overload detection forecasting.
- (f) In case of overload prediction, the LSTM model outputs a warning, sending an alarm to the Orchestrator that necessitates changes in the service performance (this action can be also performed through a Prometheus exporter).
- (g) The Orchestrator consumes data from the NWDAF and initiates the service scaling sequence to face the upcoming load increase.
- (h) The most critical components in terms of load are the controlling application server (CAS) and the participating application server (PAS). The service pods for CAS and PAS are therefore duplicated upon overload prediction received by the Orchestrator.
- (i) The MCS balances the load amongst the two instantiations of the MC service for the upcoming data traffic.

It is worth mentioning that the optimization of the scaling resources is not considered, since the operation of the MCS is based on a discrete set of deployed pods that are duplicated in case of overload prediction. Regarding the required end points (e.g. APIs) that should be developed and triggered throughout the proposed MCS-targeted controlling loop, a potential list with the associated role per endpoint can be determined as: (i) interface for model inference: An endpoint call for inferring the MCS overload detection model is required. The intrinsic functionality of this API is to receive the input samples and feed them into the model, while the result is published back to the requesting end; (ii) API for Orchestrator Notification: Another endpoint in the Orchestrator side is required to trigger a rescaling operation in case an overload alarm is raised; (iii) interface for Action Application: An API that applies the rescaling or recovery action should be implemented in the MCS provider, such that the Orchestrator-defined policy is applied to enrich the service resources and maintain service availability.

E. Generalized Prediction in Emergency Events

The overload detection analysis can be generalized in the estimation of any emergency event based on KPI degradation, following the same logic and formulating a supervised learning problem:

- 1) anomaly detection classification problem for prediction of an emergency event occurrence to allow the deployment of dedicated slice for MCS in the second scenario.
- 2) anomaly detection classification problem to forecast the need for migration of the MCS application (e.g. infrastructure failure) and deployment of edge MCS, sync with cloud, etc.

From the mathematical modeling perspective, the aforementioned problems can be jointly formulated as time series prediction. Let us denote as N_a the number of users that are already connected to the MCS application. The *RTT* metric of these UEs can be expressed as R_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_a$, since the delay depends mainly on the underlying network. For the j^{th} user, $j = 1, 2, \dots, N_c$, that wants to access the MCS application and communicate through MCPTT, we can use as KPI metric the *end-to-end (E2E) MCPTT access time* Φ_j , since it refers on the time interval of the call establishment between the user that requests the MCPTT service and the receiving user. Please also note that each MCS instance can host a maximum number of users U to exhibit an adequate service quality, i.e., $N_c + N_a \leq U$. Moreover, the R_i and Φ_j KPI metrics are time-varying variables that are acknowledged at each time instance to the monitoring component (i.e., the NWDAF telemetry module), that can analyze them as time-series and provide probability of overload warnings. The average *RTT* of the already connected users is:

$$\bar{R} = \frac{1}{N_a} \sum_{i=1}^{N_a} R_i \leq T_{RTT}, \quad (12)$$

where T_{RTT} is the *RTT* threshold in ms. Moreover, the UEs that intend to use the MCS must have an average *E2E MCPTT access time*:

$$\bar{\Phi} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \Phi_i \leq T_{E2E}, \quad (13)$$

where T_{E2E} is the threshold for the *E2E MCPTT access time* in ms. It is worth noting that a more stringent detection of emergency event may involve the KPIs of each UE instead of the average metric values across all UEs. Typical acceptable threshold values for the aforementioned metrics are 40 ms and 250 ms for the *RTT* and the *E2E MCPTT access time*, respectively [19]. Alternatively, these thresholds can be defined in a parametric way by expressing, for instance, the *RTT* threshold as the sum of the mean plus two standard deviations, i.e., $T_{RTT} = \bar{R} + std(\{R_i\})$. Therefore, the KPI Violation Occurrence (KVO) for the users that are already connected is:

$$\Upsilon_a = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \bar{R}_{t=KVO} \geq T_{RTT} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (14)$$

and the respective KVO for the UEs that have requested access to the MCS service:

$$\Upsilon_b = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \bar{\Phi}_{t=KVO} \geq T_{E2E} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (15)$$

Consequently, when the time required to access the MC service or the *RTT* time of the already active users is above each particular threshold, we can denote this time point as a KVO, signifying that better QoS is required from the MC service. The combined KVO can be determined as:

$$\Upsilon = \max\{\Upsilon_a, \Upsilon_b\} \quad (16)$$

To this end, an LSTM network can be trained by considering the previous mathematical formulation for KVO prediction. The proactive mitigation actions after the KVO forecast are to: (i) deploy a dedicated network slice for MCS according to the sequence diagram shown in Fig. 4; (ii) initiate the MC service migration sequence at the edge, as depicted in Fig. 6. These two proactive mitigation actions can be also combined, since for the multi-PoP scenario we assume that a dedicated MC slice has been already deployed in the network and that the MC UEs use this slice to access the cloud-native MC service (Fig. 5). Finally, it should be noted that the applicability of the KVO prediction method primarily depends on the availability and quality of the data used for the LSTM training (the time-series of the KPI metrics).

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, the experimental materials and methods used in this study are described. The MCS dataset was initially split into 90% for training and 10% for testing purposes before the LSTM models were trained. To this end, the ML models can be validated on testing data that have not been encountered during the training process. The initial total number of MCS users that was employed to fine-tune the LSTM hyperparameters was $U = 100$. The LSTM models presented in the following subsections were implemented in Python 3.0, using the Tensorflow (v2.4) and Scikitlearn libraries (No GPU usage).

A. Dataset Description

As aforementioned, the following three-fold metrics monitor the service-related aspects of the MCS system: Number of registered users, N_{RU} , Number of active private calls, N_{PC} and Number of active group calls, N_{GC} . These metrics are continuously sent to the NWDAF module (e.g. Prometheus server) of the telemetry system at regular time intervals (a typical monitoring sampling period of an MCS application is 30 sec). Regarding the MCS traffic dataset available for the subsequent ML model deployment, the time-series of these variables were obtained from an MCS provider company for a period of 2 months (172800 total samples per variable, sampling period 30 sec). The dataset contained 1440 epochs (each one lasting 1 hour), during which an expected overload event happened at a specific time point. The overload event is characterized by a sudden, unforeseen and rapidly-growing increase in the load traffic of the MCS system. The time point of rapid traffic increase occurrence was different across training epochs, as they reflect different cases of MCS overload scenarios.

B. Optimization of ML model Hyperparameters

The performance of the LSTM models on the problem of overload detection strongly depends on the hyperparameters of the LSTM network. The LSTM model is very sensitive to (i) the learning rate α that controls the update of the LSTM weights during the backpropagation phase of the training algorithm; (ii) the number of hidden layers that affects how deep and complex the LSTM is; (iii) the time-window length W that

Fig. 8. Training loss curves for varying values of the learning rate (α). Percentage Misclassification Error represents the training loss metric.

determines how many past metric values are used as model inputs; and (iv) the time-point C that defines the proactiveness ability of the model, i.e., the ahead of temporal model estimate of the MCS overload. The LSTM model was built with the architecture shown in Fig 7 and the following parameters were used upon extensive experimental simulations:

LSTM setup: “Adam” as optimizer (for implementing stochastic gradient descent), ‘ReLU’ as activation function of hidden units, batch size $B = 64$, number of training epochs $E = 30$. The output layer of the LSTM model had ‘Softmax’ as activation function in order to transform the output neuron value to probability, based on (10). Based on extensive simulations, the number of hidden layers was selected $N_H = 2$ as a beneficial trade-off between the LSTM network complexity, the training duration and the overload detection capability.

Fig. 8 depicts the training loss for varying values of the learning rate α with respect to the training epochs. The training loss metric shown in Fig. 8 is the Percentage Misclassification Error (PME), with quantifies the ratio of the false prediction divided by the total predictions tested. Note that, PME considers all the falsely-identified overload conditions in the nominator, including both false negatives (i.e. prediction was ‘no overload’, but actually there was overload) and false positives (i.e. prediction was ‘overload’, but actually there was no overload). Evidently, the PME of the LSTM model estimations reduces as the training phase progresses, showing optimal performance when $\alpha = 0.001$.

The fine-tuned LSTM hyperparameters are summarized in Table I. In addition, the MCS parameters that were used to label the experimental dataset for the hyperparameter tuning are also tabulated: the total number of registered users U , the group cell capacity C_{group} , the total MCS capacity C_{total} and the overload ratio r that denotes the overload occurrence, as expressed by (8) and (9). Furthermore, the decision percentage threshold D_{th} that regulates the trade-off between true and

false positives is also tabulated. Finally, the learning parameters W and C were set to 2 and 3 respectively and their direct impact on the MCS overload prediction is discussed in detail in the following subsection.

TABLE I
SETUP OF LSTM ARCHITECTURE AND PARAMETER TUNING

Parameter	Value
LSTM Optimizer	Adam
Number of hidden layers N_H	2
Neurons of 1st hidden layer	64
Neurons of 2nd hidden layer	32
Activation function of hidden and input units	ReLU
Batch size B	64
Number of training epochs E	30
Learning rate α	0.001
Activation function of output layer	Softmax
Decision percentage threshold D_{th}	0.5
Total number of MCS users U	100
Overload ratio r	0.9
Group call capacity C_{group}	5
Total MCS capacity C_{total}	90
Loss Function	Log-Loss
Lookback Window W	3 (\times 30 sec)
Proactiveness ability C	2 (\times 30 sec)

C. Impact of Lookback Window and Proactiveness Ability

Apart from the LSTM hyperparameter fine-tuning, we investigated the impact of varying Lookback Window W and Proactiveness Ability C in order to (i) evaluate how these learning parameters affect the overload detection and (ii) quantify the limitations of the LSTM model prediction. To this end, multiple LSTM setups were considered, each one being configured with a particular pair of (W, C) , where $W = 3, 6, 9$ data points and $C = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ data points. Since the sampling period was 30 sec, the tested proactiveness ability values corresponded to 1,2,3,4 and 5 minutes, respectively. Upon setting the optimal hyperparameters and training the LSTM models (α, N_H, B, E) , the resulting PME curves are shown in Fig. 9, which were extracted by calculating the PME over the testing samples. Evidently, the LSTM classifier shows optimal performance (PME of $\sim 7\%$) when $C = 2$ (1 minute), regardless of the value of the Lookback Window parameter W . As the Proactiveness Ability of the model increases ($C = 4, 6, 8, 10$), the PME metric gradually increases (up to $\sim 24\%$). The LSTM model is trained to be more proactive and perform accurate predictions well ahead of time, escalating the error ratio in the MCS overload detection. However, for a particular proactiveness ability C , the lookback window parameter also improves the PME metric, since wider W selection leads to slightly decreased classification errors ($\sim 22\%$ for $W = 9$ and $C = 10$). This may be attributed to the following: in order to provide more accurate future predictions, LSTM needs to track a wider window of past traffic patterns, with this window converging for $W = 9$. The impact of both W and C in the forecasting performance defines a clear trade-off that depends on the particular MCS key performance indicators: very timely predictions for MCS overload (i.e. high values of C) require wide lookback window (i.e. $W = 6$ or 9), which in turn come with 2 drawbacks, namely (i) lower

Fig. 9. Percentage Misclassification Error as a function of the Proactiveness Ability (C) of the LSTM for different values of the Lookback Window (W).

prediction accuracy (i.e. increased PME) and (ii) larger model complexity (i.e. increased LSTM density due to larger input values).

D. Complexity Analysis and LSTM Inference Latency

In this subsection, we provide considerations on the computation time (*time complexity*) and the memory storage requirements (*space complexity*) of the LSTM network. In this context, the space complexity is related only to spatial/storage requirements (required bytes to store the trained model) of each scheme and the density of the neural models used (number of neuronal units in the trained model).

Regarding the time complexity for training the proposed model, we assume that n is the number of the input data rows available for the LSTM model, F is the number of input features, W is the lookback window length, N_H is the number of hidden layers, $N_{U,i}$ is the number of hidden neural units of hidden layer i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N_H$), N_U is the total number of hidden neural units and E is the number of local training epochs. The training process unfolds as follows: the training data would be either passed row-by-row (Gradient Descent - GD) or would be split into several batches (Stochastic Gradient Descent - SGD) according to a predefined batch size. Each row/batch is passed as a whole to train the local model and an epoch would be completed once every row/batch was used for learning. Finally, after multiple epochs, the loss curve converges to a stable value. Thus, assuming the worst-case of row-by-row gradient calculation (i.e. the GD case), the data rows are accessed n times per epoch, whereas E epochs are performed during the training. We let $\mathcal{O}(f_{GD}(F, W, N_U))$ denote the complexity of GD, where $f_{GD}(\cdot)$ is basically the cost function as an expression of F , W and N_U and is equal to the sum of the complexities for the feedforward and backpropagation algorithmic steps of GD (they involve matrix multiplications). This cost function is encountered once a new

input row is passed, and it includes the cost for feed-forward passing and back-propagation passing a single input sample.

Since each sample is accessed E times and the total number of samples is n , the time complexity cost $\mathcal{O}(f_{GD}(F, W, N_U))$ is encountered $n \cdot E$ times. Thus, the final complexity of the LSTM scheme is $\mathcal{O}(n \cdot E \cdot f_{GD}(F, W, N_U))$, where $N_I = F \times W$ is the input layer size and the total number of hidden neural units is given by $N_U = \sum_{i=1}^{N_H} N_{U,i}$. Equivalently, the time complexity can be written as $\mathcal{O}(n \cdot E \cdot f_{GD}(N_I, \sum_{i=1}^{N_H} N_{U,i}))$. As implied by the complexity formula, the training time is proportional to the total number of training rows, the number of training epochs, and the neural network density. Noteworthy, the runtime required for training purposes is required only one time (and usually before the real operation of the model).

Regarding the convergence scheme used in this paper, we followed a threshold-based policy to terminate the training phase. Specifically, at the end of each epoch, we stored both the training loss (Log-loss computed over training samples) and the testing loss (Log-loss computed over testing samples, which were unseen by the model) curves. The Log-loss is given by (3) for both types of loss. Thus, by plotting the training and testing curves as a function of epochs, we identified the epoch for which the testing loss started to increase, independently of the training loss course. The epoch showing this attribute was the training termination epoch, so as to avoid over-fitting and keep the optimal convergence model. This termination process was conducted for multiple configurations of the hyperparameters (learning rate, number of hidden layers, LSTM density, lookback window length) to ensure optimal performance of the LSTM overload detector.

Once the LSTM model is trained, it can -almost effortlessly- be inferred multiple times (inference requires only some arithmetic operations). To measure the average inference latency of the LSTM model, we computed the mean latency across 100 individual latency metrics extracted by inferring 100 testing samples. We observed that the mean latency was 0.92 sec, with the minimum and the maximum latency being 0.74 sec and 1.15 sec, respectively. It is important to highlight that, in this specific case, the prediction made in time point t refers to the upcoming time point of $t + 30$ sec, which means that the inference result is available much earlier than the potential time point of overload occurrence. In this way, if the proactiveness ability of the LSTM is high (here 30 sec), the delay of inference is quite negligible (here 0.92 sec), since it totally overlaps with the forecasting period.

E. Comparison among Overload Detectors

This subsection compares the validation results of different overload detection schemes after setting the LSTM model with the best hyperparameter configuration (according to Table I), using $W = 3$ and $C = 2$. The comparisons include both learning-based and deterministic rule-based schemes, which are described below:

- *Random Decision Forest-based Overload Detector (RDF)*: This is an ensemble learning classifier that is constructed by multiple decision tree models (here 10 models). Each out of 10 tree models was trained on the

Fig. 10. Percentage Misclassification Error achieved by the six classification schemes (LSTM, SVM, RDF, MLR, FD-DOD, T-DOD), sorted in ascending order.

10% samples of the dataset. For a given sample, RDF predicts ‘anomaly’ if the majority of the tree models predict ‘anomaly’.

- *Support Vector Machine-based Overload Detector (SVM)*: This supervised learning model is used for (non-)linear classification. Given the training samples consisting of both ‘anomaly’ and ‘normal’ classes, it finds a hyperplane that maximally separates the two classes in two areas. Every new sample is predicted as ‘anomaly’ if it falls in the area of ‘anomalies’.
- *LSTM-based Overload Detector*: This is a non-linear classifier, whose architecture is shown in Fig. 7 and fine-tuned parameters presented in the previous subsection.
- *Multivariable Logistic Regression (MLR) Overload Detector*: This method assumes a sigmoid-shaped relation between multiple inputs and binary probabilistic output, and finds the sigmoid equation that best fits the class labels.
- *First-Derivative-based Deterministic Overload Detector (FD-DOD)*: This classifier predicts ‘overload’ class deterministically when a positive first-derivative value of $N_{PC} + N_{GC}$ is observed for two consecutive time points, indicating a steady increase in traffic due to the occurrence of an emergency event, otherwise predicts ‘no overload’.
- *Threshold-based Deterministic Overload Detector (T-DOD)*: The overload condition occurs when the number of active users (participating in private or group calls) exceeds the total MCS capacity C_{total} , based on (8) and (9). This detector predicts the ‘overload’ class constantly when $N_{PC} + N_{GC}$ reaches 80% of C_{total} , to ensure overload alarms are timely provided.

Fig. 10 shows how accurately each scheme can detect overload situations, assessed on the testing (validation) dataset. The PME for the six overload detection frameworks is calculated as the fraction of incorrect predictions (the sum of false positive

and false negative predictions) against the total number of test samples. The LSTM classifier has the best performance among all the schemes, showing a PME of 7.1% with regards to the detection of the overload condition. SVM and RDF models were the second and the third anomaly classifiers in terms of PME (9.7% and 11.3%, respectively). Note that, RDF was implemented as the ensemble model across 10 decision trees, where the number of trees was selected upon extensive simulations. The MLR method also exhibits a relatively good performance (11.8%) in the prediction of overload occurrence. Moreover, the FD-DOD and T-DOD methods, which are static rule-based algorithms, have acceptable PMEs (14.6% and 19.8%, respectively), mainly due to their predefined policy.

Regarding the learning-based schemes, LSTM is shown to better approximate the relation between the traffic patterns and the overload classes, thus providing more accurate overload alarms, as compared with the SVM, RDF and MLR detectors. Evidently, the LSTM model also outperforms the rule-based methods, since it learns from the data itself and, hence, is able to capture the MCS traffic anomalies during the training phase of the algorithm using many overload epochs. On the other hand, the rule-based methods do not need any training process and they can still be effortlessly deployed without much computational cost (they only involve simple mathematical computations). In addition, the LSTM models only need to be trained once so as to estimate the function $f_{LSTM(\cdot)}$, and, in case of a requirement for refreshing the LSTM weights, they can be softly retrained on new samples (using the pretrained model parameters as initial weights). This process can guarantee effortless adaptation of the LSTM to new and up-to-date alarming behaviors. Hence, even though the rule-based and deterministic methods can offer low-complexity solutions, the results indicate that the LSTM models can be safely considered as the best option for non-linear timeseries classification problems, especially for the overload prediction case.

F. The Impact of Service-Level Agreements

So far, the algorithmic and architectural setup has only taken into consideration a dedicated MCS network deployment (or a single network slice), which is assisted by a single LSTM in order to detect overload of the service (Scenario 1 of Section III). Specifically, previous sections used fixed values of the parameters $D_{th} = 0.5$ and $r = 0.9$ and investigated the impact of parameters W and C . However, the presented framework is general-purpose and can be easily modified according to different service-level agreement (SLA) requirements (e.g., the deployment of a firefighting team requires ultra-reliable communications). In principle, an SLA is a contract between a service provider and its customers (in this case, the first-responders) that defines the service standards that the provider is obligated to meet.

In this subsection, we consider four single-slice scenarios, each one considering different MCS-related SLAs. Thus, every scenario-dependent MCS requires different SLAs with its potential MCS users. We assume also that each MCS is controlled by an LSTM model for overload detection purposes,

so as to ensure minimum SLA violation (i.e., ideally all SLA requirements should be satisfied). To concretely illustrate the generality of the proposed LSTM framework in terms of the MCS overload detection, four diverse scenarios are considered with the SLA descriptions which are tabulated in Table II. More specifically, the following scenarios are assumed:

- **Scenario 1 - Ultra-Sensitivity in Overload Detection (USOD):** This scenario designs an MCS to support at most 100 registered users, with the overload occurring when more than 90 users are active. Also, a PME below 10% is required. Finally, there is a strict requirement for the MCS to present a high ratio of 99.9% in the identification of overload condition, i.e. 99.9% true positive ratio of class ‘Anomaly’. This means that the MCS should identify almost all the overload conditions, thus it should be very sensitive in deciding the class ‘Overload’.
- **Scenario 2 - Ultra-Efficiency in Resource Utilization (UERU):** As opposed to scenario 1, here the target is to provide an MCS that is as much resource-utilization-efficient as possible. This means that there is a strict requirement to present high precision (99%) when the prediction is ‘Overload’, otherwise, if MCS presents a high false positive ratio, then the MCS re-scaling action will result in excessive resource waste. Also, MCS should serve at most 100 registered users with a PME below 10%.
- **Scenario 3 - Support of Massive Users (SMU):** This scenario follows the same requirements as in scenarios 1 and 2, but there is no strict constraints about high or low false positive rate (thus $D_{th} = 0.5$). The requirement here is to support massive users ($U \geq 700$), so as to test the degree to which the LSTM framework can scale up in terms of the number of users.
- **Scenario 4 - Ultra-Proactiveness in Overload Detection (UPOD):** This scenario requires the MCS to be as proactive as possible, demanding a timely and accurate prediction (PME below 10%) 2 minutes before the overload occurrence. At most 100 registered users shall be supported.

TABLE II
DESCRIPTION AND REQUIREMENT OF MULTIPLE SLA-SPECIFIC SLICES

Scenario	SLA Description	Parameters
1: USOD	Req1: At most 100 registered users; Req2: PME <10%; Req3: Identification ratio of overload condition is 99.9%	$U = 100$ $W = 3$ $C = 2$ $D_{th} = 0.2$
2: UERU	Req1: At most 100 registered users; Req2: PME <10%; Req3: Precision of 99.9% when predicting ‘Overload’	$U = 100$ $W = 3$ $C = 2$ $D_{th} = 0.8$
3: SMU	Req1: At least 700 registered users; Req2: PME <10%; Req3: Balance between false and true positives	$U = 800$ $W = 3$ $C = 2$ $D_{th} = 0.5$
4: UPOD	Req1: At most 100 registered users; Req2: PME <10%; Req3: Predictions should be provided 6 min before overload occurrence	$U = 100$ $W = 6$ $C = 6$ $D_{th} = 0.5$

The third column of Table II defines the proper parameter

regulation of the LSTM, so as to achieve the desired SLAs per scenario. In specific, the special regulation towards achieving high sensitivity in scenario 1 is to set D_{th} to a low value (here 0.2) in order to make the LSTM biased to the ‘Overload’ class. This means that the LSTM is expected to prefer most of the time the ‘Overload’ alarm, leading to a very high true positive rate (i.e. all true overload conditions will be predicted by the model). On the contrary, this setup will result in excessive resource waste, given that it will also present high false positive ratio, thus invoking the Orchestrator to unnecessarily scale up the resources. In a similar sense, scenario 2 demands high precision in predicting ‘Overload’, so as to ensure that when an alarm is triggered, the upcoming resource deployment is not unnecessary. Scenario 3 requires massive users, thus $U = 800$ that are able to register in the MCS are considered. Finally, the proactiveness required by scenario 4 is achieved by setting $C = 6$ with a consequent regulation of $W = 6$ to ensure low PME, as suggested by Fig. 9.

By training a single LSTM per scenario, each one parameterized as defined in Table II, all the resulting models were tested on a 100-epoch dataset that was not encountered during the training. To measure the degree to which the models satisfy the 3 different requirements of each scenario (Req1, Req2, Req3), 4 metrics were extracted, as shown in Fig. 11. The percentage SLA satisfaction $SS(Req_i)$ quantifies the fulfillment ratio of requirement i according to the following formula:

$$SS(Req_i) = \frac{x_{achieved}(Req_i)}{x_{target}(Req_i)} \quad (17)$$

where $x_{target}(Req_i)$ and $x_{achieved}(Req_i)$ is the target and achieved value, respectively, of requirement i (where $i = 1, 2, 3$ and the requirements are defined in Table II per scenario). Also, for each scenario, the total SLA satisfaction metric was extracted as the average across $SS(Req_1)$, $SS(Req_2)$ and $SS(Req_3)$. As depicted in Fig. 11, all scenarios succeeded to fully guarantee the Req1 (number of MCS users), with the LSTM presenting exceptional performance even when a large number (800) of MCS users are considered (scenario 3). Also, scenario 4 exhibited an SLA violation of 9% in Req2, since the necessity to achieve a proactiveness of 3 minutes ($C = 6$) degrades the overall PME (see also Fig. 9 for explanation). In scenario 1, the low value of D_{th} succeeded to fulfill the Req3 by simultaneously violating the Req2 by about 9%. This is attributed to the fact that it is not feasible to both increase the true positive ratio and decrease the PME, because when D_{th} is low, the probability of false positives increases as well. The same stands for scenario 2 where D_{th} is high, which means that, to ensure high precision of the model, the PME-related requirement is slightly violated (about 12% violation).

Overall, the presented results demonstrated the ability of the proposed MCS detector to be easily adapted in different SLA profiles by properly adjusting the parameters W , C , D_{th} and U . At the same time, in order to satisfy strict requirements regarding the sensitivity (scenario 1), precision (scenario 2) and proactiveness (scenario 4) of the MCS, the overall PME should slightly degrade by about 10%. Also, the algorithm is fully operative when considering dense user

Fig. 11. SLA satisfaction (%) achieved by the LSTM algorithm in the four scenarios exhibiting diverse requirements.

scenarios (scenario 3), exhibiting no SLA violations. Finally, the total SLA satisfaction was constantly higher than 95% in all scenarios.

VII. CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This work presents three architectural scenarios for deploying and scaling MC services in 5G and beyond networks, leveraging recent technological advances like CNFs and network slicing. These frameworks aim to empower MC services during emergencies by meeting strict KPIs for network reliability and latency. The scenarios include an MC service load increase and scaling scheme, a dedicated MC slice for PPDR users, and an MC service migration scenario at the edge, with proposed sequence diagrams for network deployments.

Furthermore, the MC service load increase scenario showcases the use of an LSTM model to predict emergency events using real-time datasets. The model’s real-time inference capability for overload detection can be adapted for identifying temporal variations and anomalies, improving network reliability and PPDR communications security. The MCS overload detection problem is mathematically formulated, and the LSTM network’s architecture and key performance parameters are examined. The LSTM’s prediction capabilities are compared to other classifiers, demonstrating its superiority. The algorithm’s adaptability is confirmed through four scenarios with different SLA requirements, showing the LSTM model’s flexibility in achieving high performance with minor adjustments.

In the proposed scenarios, several potential bottlenecks could impact the performance and reliability of the network: (i) Orchestrator Responsiveness: The Orchestrator’s ability to re-configure network resources quickly and efficiently is crucial, particularly in scenarios involving sudden load increases or emergency events. Any delays or inefficiencies in Orchestrator responsiveness could lead to service disruptions or failures;

(ii) NWDAF Processing Capabilities: The NWDAF plays a key role in monitoring network performance and triggering necessary actions. However, if the NWDAF is unable to process and analyze data rapidly enough, there could be delays in detecting and responding to network anomalies, potentially leading to degraded service quality; (iii) Edge to Cloud Coordination: Coordinating between edge nodes and centralized cloud servers, especially during service migrations, poses significant challenges. Latency and bandwidth limitations could become bottlenecks, particularly in scenarios requiring the synchronization of stateful services across multiple nodes.

Depending on the aforementioned capabilities, we have identified the best-case and worst-case scenarios for the proposed deployment options in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential outcomes under different conditions:

Best-case Scenario: In optimal conditions, predictive algorithms within NWDAF preemptively detect potential network overloads or failures. The Orchestrator then successfully scales resources or migrates services without any noticeable disruption to end-users. For instance, in Scenario 2, a dedicated MCS slice is dynamically allocated and fully operational before any service degradation occurs.

Worst-case Scenario: In contrast, the worst-case scenario involves a catastrophic network failure where the Orchestrator is unable to scale or migrate services in time, leading to significant service disruption. For instance, in Scenario 3, if the service relocation time exceeds the tolerable limit due to unforeseen delays in network reconfiguration, the MCS may experience severe outages or performance degradation.

As the transition to beyond 5G networks is imminent, several open research questions arise regarding the provision of MCS. Key areas of ongoing investigation include the development of robust and scalable network architectures that can ensure URLLC under diverse and dynamic conditions. Additionally, the integration of advanced technologies such as network slicing, edge computing, and AI/ML for real-time decision-making and resource allocation poses significant challenges. Another critical topic is to ensure end-to-end security and privacy in MCS, especially in scenarios involving mMTC and IoT. Finally, the impact of beyond 5G networks on the interoperability of legacy systems and the standardization of protocols for seamless communication across heterogeneous networks remain relevant research topics.

In this context, future works may expand on the findings presented in this paper, refining and implementing the presented models and architectures in practical network scenarios. In specific, the future directions can build on this work: (i) investigation of security methods for heterogeneous devices and different vendors that provide components in an integrated network architecture, including the authentication of edge nodes; (ii) end-to-end slice management that is vividly expanded to the RAN resources through resource allocation algorithm (managing the energy-efficient at the radio, the UE association schemes, etc); (iii) integration of ML techniques that enable the collaborative learning and provide by default further data privacy (e.g., Federated Learning (FL) approach); (iv) utilization of the practical implementation guidelines to

quantify how the architectural deployments boost the reliability and the latency of MCS communications.

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